

PLANNING OF GREEN AREAS IN CITY AREAS

Otabek Umarov Zulfikarovich

Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction, associate
professor

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2913-4378>

bekolmas@mail.ru

***Abstract.** The rapid development of the city in vertical and horizontal directions sharply reduces the attractiveness of the landscape of the area. Interesting natural objects - parks, beautiful hills, banks of rivers and lakes, terraces on the plain, if they are preserved and organically included in the system of urban green spaces, in forming the environment of the architectural and planning structure of the city can play an important role. architectural and planning structure of the city. The beautiful landscape, the color over time, the fragrance of flowers, the rustling of leaves have a beneficial effect on the psychological and physical state of a person, his mood and nervous system, and help create comfortable living conditions for a person in the city.*

***Key words:** urban environment, green space, green area, relief, industrial area, sanitary protection area, green belt, regular design, landscape, natural objects.*

Introduction. Throughout the history of urban development, various ideas have been put forward to include natural areas in urban planning. Some of them have not lost their importance even in our time. Experts distinguish three main periods, which are fundamentally different in their approach to solving this problem. The first of them begins with the emergence of cities and ends in the 19th century. Systems of green areas had regular geometric (circular, concentric, etc.) contours (schemes of J. Perret, G. Sharpe, C. Fourier). They were considered without taking into account the external environment of the city. The second period is associated with the emergence of large industrial centers and the birth of agglomerations (the end of the 19th century - the first half of the 20th century). New architecture-

planning solutions for cities demanded the development of a system of green areas in the form of green zones, green fields, diameters, etc. (T. Fritsch, E. Howard, R. Envin, S. Shestakov, I. schemes). Leonidov, Le Corbusier, P. Abercrombie and others). Currently, the search for the optimal ratio of built-up and green spaces is underway. Attention is paid to the sanitary, hygienic, aesthetic and recreational role of green areas. Green areas around the city began to be included in the city master plans. The third period (2nd half of the 20th century) is distinguished from previous periods by a comprehensive approach to the design of the city and its surrounding areas[1].

In cities, more than 50% of the territory, and in microdistricts, up to 70% of the total area should be allocated to irrigated green areas, which combine individual buildings, structures and their groups into microdistrict or massif ensembles.

Main part: In the modern city, flexible planning structures capable of responding to changing needs and conditions are used, therefore, the systems of urban green areas are constantly becoming more complex and their individual elements are increasingly different.

If a small city has, as a rule, one multi-functional park and several urban parks, avenues and squares, then as the city grows, the types, sizes and functions of the objects of its landscaping system will change. The difference in [2] increases.

The variety of urban development systems in use is determined by the presence of specific urban development conditions - the location of the city in the system of group settlements; national economic profile; the size of the territory and the adopted zoning scheme; placement of community centers, residential construction, industry; architectural-planning solution of the area; traffic route map; the possibility of organizing a single system of green areas of the city and its green zone, development prospects. Natural-climatic, sanitary-hygiene, landscape-ecological, physical-geographic and some other factors play an important role.

The formation and development of urban green spaces is influenced by the natural features of the area: climate, topography, available vegetation, soil, presence of reservoirs, geological and hydrological conditions. Among the climatic features, radiation, temperature, wind regimes, amount of precipitation, wind speed and direction are of primary importance. The degree of influence of various factors on landscaping techniques varies in each individual case[3]. In this case, a special place is given to the comprehensive assessment of the current state of the city's environment.

Depending on urban planning and natural conditions, the urban greening system can be in the form of green "spots" evenly distributed throughout the city, several large green roads - entering the city center; water-green diameter (park system, boulevards, open spaces along the plain of the river crossing the city); one or more lines of green spaces extending along the building, sometimes the lines are located transversely, dividing the city into segments (with linear development of the city); green areas surrounding individual urban areas (with a decentralized urban planning scheme)[3].

Green areas, organically included in the development structure, improve the structural, planning, architectural and artistic features of the city, help to create an expressive volumetric-spatial image of the city, a beautiful silhouette.

The influence of natural factors on the formation of the city is especially noticeable in new small cities dominated by the landscape - for example, the water-green diameter, which becomes the main compositional axis of the city.

The urban development system should ensure a relatively uniform distribution of seedlings in settlements, settlements and microdistricts, public and cultural centers, production and sanitary protection zones.

The formation of the system of urban green areas is influenced by: the ratio of built-up and open urban areas; the share of existing seedlings, their quality and

their place in the city planning structure; size and fragmentation of individual green spaces, their functional role; landscape features; traffic and pedestrian convenience.

The connection between the plots of urban and suburban green areas is carried out with the help of continuous avenues, banks, pedestrian avenues, green lines along highways, special protective lines that together with water reservoirs form water-green diameters, green systems. . lines, dividing the urban development equally in the direction of favorable winds and river currents, connecting the central urban areas with the green zone of the city[4].

Consolidation of green spaces is currently the most important requirement for the formation of urban green space systems. It is advisable to introduce more than 100 m wide green spaces in the city, which will divide the urban development into areas of about 1000 hectares. According to the researchers, the landscaping system of a large city should have at least 50-100 hectares of green spaces that provide optimal conditions for the growth of trees and shrubs. Cities located in natural settings, where existing green areas can be integrated into the urban structure, should develop the best qualities of the natural landscape through optimal planning solutions and greening.

Hygienic and decorative qualities of plants are formed for a long time and are largely determined by the development of the original idea included in the system of green spaces in the city and the architectural-planning solution of individual objects [5]. In order to achieve the best healing effect and create normal conditions for the development of plants, the system of urban green spaces should take into account the current state of the environment, as well as the possibility of changing it in connection with the planned development of the city. The results of the environmental assessment are applied to urban plans in the form of graphic diagrams. By combining the schemes of each of the analyzes carried out, a comprehensive assessment is given. This method is successfully used in planning options for solutions.

In cities with adverse wind conditions, special planting plays an important role to protect against strong winds, dust storms and dry winds to improve the microclimate. Windproof landscape design is formed in the form of a closed landscape.

It is necessary to apply scientific-based schemes for the placement and organization of sanitary protection zones in cities with permanent sources of pollution, and to implement the improvement of production, utility and transport areas.

Sanitary protection zones between industrial and residential areas are created in the form of lines perpendicular to the prevailing wind directions. Green spaces are placed in cities taking into account the creation of an optimal aeration regime. Specially oriented wide avenues and green areas improve the ventilation of the building and prevent stagnation of polluted air in the lowlands[6].

The relative location of open and green spaces allows to regulate heat balance and create air convection points in cities. In order to ensure aeration of the urban area with favorable winds, spaces are created in green areas in the direction of prevailing winds, integrated into the landscape composition in the form of a system of meadows and water spaces. In the architectural and planning solution of the urban area, it is necessary to take into account the possibility that nearby water bodies and green areas can create ventilation paths that have a significant impact on the microclimate. The aeration process of built-up urban areas is significantly improved as a result of the decompaction of buildings on the banks of reservoirs and borders of green spaces and the opening of the inner space of residential areas to the water surface and greenery. Urban development, which takes into account the natural mountain breezes that occur at night in the conditions of mountainous and high mountain terrain, allows to significantly remove pollutants accumulated during the day from industrial enterprises and vehicles. Wide streets located on the mountainside, directed along the direction of the prevailing winds (with a deviation

of up to 20 °), help to increase the wind speed by 10-30% compared to the wind speed in the open area.

The emergence of new cities, as a rule, is associated with the development of industry, and their development has its own characteristics, determined by the specific characteristics of specific technological processes used in a certain production.

There are areas of disturbed land (quarries, mines, landfills, etc.) that are used for the expansion of green spaces in cities with mining enterprises located in the area of abandoned mines and mines. Their landscape is made with gas-resistant plants that do not require soil and moisture.

In cities with non-hazardous branches of industry (instrument manufacturing, optics, fine mechanics), greening works are carried out in order to protect production from dust and air pollution that occurs in settlements. The assortment of trees and shrubs in so-called reverse sanitary protection zones should exclude light-fruited plants that are carried by the wind and release pollen during flowering.

The creation of green areas in cities with unfavorable natural conditions (deserts, areas with steep relief) is complicated by the complexity of the necessary planting work and subsequent plant care. In oasis cities, artificial landscaping systems shade pedestrian links between residential complexes and urban attractions in conditions of excessive insolation, planting plants in relatively small areas near residential, commercial and community centers, along canal boulevards. , compact placement in the form of irrigation ditches is recommended.

Cities located among shrinking agricultural land develop green space systems combining economic and recreational functions.

In river valleys, on water banks, and in cities without greenery, they use reclaimed water - artificially restored areas.

In the system of urban green spaces, areas for short-term recreation, mainly forest-park zones, places for daily recreation can be allocated in suburban areas located near housing, city centers and workplaces. In this case, easy accessibility, good sanitation and microclimatic conditions and beautiful landscapes should be taken into account.

A special regime for the protection and transformation of landscapes is established for monuments of landscape horticultural art and unique natural landscapes, in order to maximize the preservation of natural nature, to create favorable conditions for its protection from excess water flow, "conservation zones" are separated. visitors and the impact of industrial and transport emissions. "Buffer zones" are being created that absorb large recreational loads and attract visitors[7].

Permission to place buildings, structures and communications not related to visitor services in the areas of parks, forest parks, national and natural parks, protected areas of cultural and natural monuments doesn't smile.

Conclusion: In the master plan of the city's development, the formation of a system of green areas is envisaged for an approximate period of 25-30 years. Periodic stabilization of urban boundaries allows the growth of trees and shrubs in the green belt, limits the growth of buildings and the consolidation of settlements. At the end of the estimated period, the city boundary will be expanded by adding the areas behind the existing green belt.

During the expansion of the city, green belt green areas (forest parks, courtyards and gardens, parks, etc.) within the limits of its residential area are transformed into urban green areas with new functions. it is planned to be turned over and built in their place. New green belts will be created within the new city limits.

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Issue 3 <https://newarticle.ru/index.php/bnss>